

March 2023

Church Administration:

Critical Analysis of Children Assemblies

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- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.20448766](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20448766)

Abstract:

Church Administration has gotten a pretty wide scope in studies, being the government of assemblies that formulate and ensure implementation of policies for optimal performance. Churches or denomination varies with each having its own structural characteristic, such as: episcopal, connexional, presbyterian, and congregational. It is one thing to have other spiritual gifts; it is another to possess administrative tenacity which is also a gift from God. The former can bring in new members into church, while the later will ensure old and new members have gotten no reason to leave. Denominational differences notwithstanding; Administrative tenacity determines the possible growth of any gathering, little wonder why some remain static, some growing and others becoming mega churches. Critiquing levels of deliberate attention given to children assembly, primary data sources Quantitative and Qualitative research employed, deductive reasoning as well as interpretative study focusing on analytical observation of practices and behaviors. This Study confirms that children play vital roles in church growth; visual aids, instructional materials, role play and service replication is imperative in children churches. The more we develop our children churches, the greater positive impact it has on church and spiritual growth of the pearl. The Redeemed Christian Bible College (RCBC) and some seminaries for instance have being playing critical role on this; however this study brings more to the table, in terms of policy recommendations and field implementation.

Introduction:

Administration is the structure for policy making and decision upholding, either individual or organizational. God sure rule in the affairs on men but the decisions we make or fail to make determine how far or fast we can go. Administration is derived from the word 'Administer' this word is rooted in the Latin word 'ad' + 'ministraire'. This implies the care for people to manage affair. It is the organization and direction of human and material resources to achieve desired goal effectively. (Olubanji 2021, p. 4) It involves the system, processes and dynamics of managing the affairs and resources of an organization to achieving cooperate or organizational goal. Engaging in common sets of functions to meet organizational goal. This include Planning, Organizing, Staffing, Directing, etc

Hence, Church Administration; (Dale 2008, p. 25) church administration involves the growing or empowering individuals to realize their goals or potential. While churches are religious gathering, to some that's the only social environment they can be, having let go of the things of the world. Suffice to say, administrative tenacity in our churches have a way it reflect greatly in the growth and in the life of members. The proclivity of Nigerian mega churches is not only in terms of their grandiose edifices, but also their religious innovations, creativity and development initiatives in the various communities where they are situated. (Adedibu 2023, p. 1) Many thanks to Professor Adedibu for pointing this out, these churches are sure not building only structures but people too. Depression is real, population of people committing suicide will have been higher but for the sake of positive energies coming from churches, several environments will not have known development if not for the churches in those locals. This growth in churches has impacted positively the environment and people.

This study opine that since church administration has effect of the people, it's worthy of note that the larger the congregation the more people that will be impacted. Pastor E. A. Adeboye requested for 'ninety-eight (98) people to donate N1000.00 each to join him and his wife' and he promised to give each donor plots of land to

build their individual houses. (Adedibu, B.A., 2019, p. 3) These 98 people definitely had been impacted positively by the church; like minded people having land around themselves, as at then one can conveniently number estate structured residents, unlike this age and time. This 1983 memorandum of understanding goes beyond having effect on the offeror and offeree only (as self administrators), but the families and precisely the children.

Statistic has it that currently; Nigeria and Kenya have been declared capitals of mega churches as 66.5% of the 119 mega churches in Africa are based in the two countries, with Lagos having 14 of these mega churches (Burgess 2020b, p. 246). Small churches impact small number of persons, mega churches definitely will impact larger number of persons. Strategies varies, some churches had better grow, while some are growing bigger every day. Other variable for church growth will feature in subsequent write ups; children churches are the core for this research work.

This Study argues that for church to grow; administrative tenacity is required and in one of the critical sector of the assembly which is children auditorium, what the administrators do or fail to do, impact the children, families and the church growth. Children talks! What happens in children church forms discursion, on the way home from church, among peers all through the week, if obnoxious they say, if fascinating they say too. Children remarkably grow churches, when their energies are harnessed appropriately. They want to play and have fun? Yes, it is possible for them to do this structurally and still learn.

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